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**An Investigation into Syncretic Beliefs and Practices Amongst
Christians in Ondo State Nigeria; With Special Reference to Christian
Participation in the Aringinya Festival of Yoruba Speaking People of
Ikare-Akoko**

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***Abstract:** This study investigated syncretic Beliefs and practices amongst Christians in Ondo State Nigeria; with special reference to Christian participation in the Aringinya Festival of Yoruba speaking People of Ikare-Akoko. This study employed a survey research design method. The population of the study comprises of all Christians members (Orthodox Church and Pentecostal Churches) in the Ikare local government councils of the state. The sample of the study comprised Christians leaving in Ikare Akoko. Out of all the registered Churches in Ikare only twenty Churches which would be made up of ten Orthodox Churches and 10 Pentecostal Churches in Ikare Akoko. The simple random sampling was used. The research instrument that was adopted for this study was questionnaire. The instrument was face validated by three experts, three from the Department of Arts and Religious Education of University of Abuja. Since the three clusters contain non-dichotomously scored items, the internal consistency of the clusters were determined using Cronbach Alpha. The internal consistency reliability estimate yielded 0.90 and 0.85. The result obtained from the questionnaire was computed and analyzed using descriptive statistics. The study showed that Yoruba Christian in Ikare Akoko engaged in the following syncretism practices; secret cults/societies, belief in and practice of witchcraft, belief in black magic; charms and amulets, belief in ancestral/hero*

worship, belief in oracles/fortune telling; belief and participation in traditional festivals/rituals (oro ile). The study also revealed reasons for Yoruba Christians in Ikare Akoko are participating in the annual ritual Aringinya festival to include; for protection, child bearing (lack of patience), riches and wealth, power and healing, cultural tied, great harvest, poverty and materialism. Based on the findings, the study recommends that the curriculum of the various Christians theology institutions could be overhauled with a view to meeting the modern challenges of education that are more relevant to the society. The few among these graduates educating and teaching against these practices should not relent in their efforts to eradicate syncretism among Yoruba society.

Key words: Aringinya Festival, Christians, syncretic Beliefs

Introduction

The South-West geopolitical zone of Nigeria is made up of six (6) states, namely, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Ekiti, Lagos and Ogun States with one hundred and thirty seven (137) Local Government Areas (LGAs). Ondo state has eighteen (18) LGAs, Osun state with thirty (30) LGAs, Oyo has thirty three (33) LGAs, Ekiti state with sixteen (16) LGAs, Lagos state with twenty (20) LGAs and Ogun state with twenty (20) LGAs respectively (Faith, 2018). The population of the entire region according to the 2006 population census is about thirty eight (38) million people. Apart from agriculture as the mainstay of economic activities for the majority in the rural communities, the zone is also known for its commerce and trading activities with a preponderance of micro, small and medium indigenous industries that are into manufacturing, fabrication and agro-allied produce.

(Odejebi 14), posited that Christianity is the most popular and most advertised religion in Nigeria and especially in Yoruba land. It was introduced in the middle of the nineteenth century by devote missionaries from Britain whose mission was though commerce they came preaching the message of Christ, ministering to the people and also healing the sick, this was what actually pulled the crowd to them in the first place. They started from the eastern part of the country which is populated by the Igbos. They infiltrated the village councils and chiefs, who gave them lands to build local churches. Before the 80s the Christian religion had spread to the southern part of the country, to the Yorubas and the middle belt (Benin).

The Yoruba people of South-west Nigeria whether Christians or Islam are known for practicing syncretism. (Bashorun 22) submits that “Yorubas nowadays may be practising Christians or Muslims, but there are still shrines to the old gods scattered around the countryside, and traditional festivals – like the festival of the Oro cult...are still celebrated and still taken extremely seriously. As in many parts of West Africa that practise this type of cult, women and outsiders are forbidden to look at the masked figures”. The average Yoruba man or Woman looks at religion as a panacea and final succor for nearly every problem in his or her life. He also appreciates forces in nature that work against the benevolence of the Supreme Being. Hopeless in the face of these forces, he seeks help in terms of intermediaries; his conceived conglomerate of gods.

(Onah, Eze and Nnadi 31) submitted that the syncretism that is common among Yoruba people of Ondo state is festival practice. My curiosity arises out of the fact that Ondo historically, is one of the ancient and oldest Christians States in the south–west of Nigeria, and one still finds quite a large proportion of Yoruba Christians mixing their Christians religion with traditional beliefs and practices.

It is my hope that by embarking on this work, Yoruba Christians in Ondo State especially those Christian in Ikare Akoko and in general Christians will be more enlightened about those things that can adversely affect their Christianity beliefs and can also affect their *relationship* negatively with God, which is the basis, the bone, marrow and the focus of Christians and its foundation. Based on this, this study seeks to investigate syncretic Beliefs and practices amongst Christians in Ondo State Nigeria; with special reference to the Aringinya Festival of Yoruba speaking People of Ikare-Akoko.

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The Purpose of this study is to investigate into syncretic Beliefs and practices amongst Christians in Ondo State Nigeria; with special reference to Christian participation in the Aringinya Festival of Yoruba speaking People of Ikare-Akoko. The study shall naturally investigate various causes of syncretism among Yoruba Christians of Ikare - Akoko and to identify strategies needed by churches to reduce such practices.

In specific terms the objectives of the study are to:

1. To find out the various syncretism practices Yoruba Christian in Ikare Akoko are involved;
2. To identify the reasons for involving in the Aringinya festival in Ikare Akoko as a Christian;

1.3 Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in the study:

1. What are the various syncretism practices Yoruba Christian in Ikare Akoko are involved?
2. What are reasons for involving in the Aringinya festival in Ikare Akoko as a Christian?

2.0 Method

This study employed a survey research design method. This is because of the population size and the nature of the research which involves using the sample for the study and generating the result of data obtained from the sample. The samples of the study also possess the same characteristics of the population. The population of the study comprises of all Christians members (Orthodox Church and Pentecostal Churches) in the Ikare local government councils of the state. The sample of the study comprised Christians leaving in Ikare Akoko. Out of all the registered Churches in Ikare only twenty Churches which would be made up of ten Orthodox Churches and 10 Pentecostal Churches in Ikare Akoko. The researcher used twenty Churches made up of Orthodox Churches and Pentecostal Churches in Ikare local government council. Ten respondents were chosen per Church which included one Pastor and ten Church Members totaling two hundred and twenty respondents. The simple random sampling was used. The research instrument that was adopted for this study was questionnaire. The questionnaire was titled "An Investigation into syncretic Beliefs and Practices amongst Christians Questionnaire." (AISBPCQ). The Questionnaire was structured questionnaire, developed along the lines of the research questions formulated for study. The questionnaire was divided into three sections.

The instrument was face validated by three experts, three from the Department of Arts and Religious Education of University of Abuja. The experts were requested to assess the suitability of the language; and relevance of the items in addressing the research questions bearing in mind the purpose of the study. Their corrections and advice gave rise to the modification of the drafts and the final draft. The instrument was trial tested using Pastors from Owo local government of the State which is outside the area of study. Since the three clusters contain non-dichotomously scored items, the internal consistency of the clusters were determined using Cronbach Alpha. The internal consistency reliability

estimate yielded 0.90 and 0.85. The instrument had an overall reliability estimate of 0.97 which indicates that the instrument is reliable. The direct delivery and retrieval method was employed in the administration of the instruments. Three trained research assistants were employed to assist the researcher in the administration of the instrument. The two main methods employed for data collection which are the primary and secondary methods. Data collected was presented by using both quantitative and qualitative methods. The result obtained from the questionnaire was computed and analyzed using descriptive statistics. The output was summarized and tabulated for easy presentation, assessment and interpretation using descriptive statistics as can be seen in the preceding chapter.

3.0 Result and Discussion

Research Question One: What are the various syncretic practices Yoruba Christian in Ikare Akoko are involved?

Table one: Answer to research question one

S/N	The following are the various syncretic practices among Christian in Ikare -Akoko	Pastors						Church Members					
		SA	A	SD	D	X	S.D	SA	A	D	SD	X	D.S
1	Practice of secret cults/societies	52	21	0	0	3.16	0.98	348	129	84	28	3.35	0.99
2	Belief in and practice of witchcraft	248	18	4	0	3.04	0.87	388	189	38	11	3.12	0.93
3	Belief in black magic ; charms and amulets	50	22	6	1	2.94	0.75	328	207	38	9	3.10	0.90
4	Belief in ancestral /hero worship	52	18	0	1	3.05	0.89	308	213	60	38	3.02	0.93
5	Belief in oracles /fortune telling	32	21	8	3	2.97	0.88	368	222	38	7	3.15	0.98
6	Belief and participation	64	12	0	0	3.13	0.99	448	219	63	6	3.23	0.95

	in traditional festivals /rituals (<i>oro ile</i>)												
		Total mean				3.33							

Source: Fieldwork 2022

The data on table one above reveals the mean rating of pastors and Church members in Ikare Akoko in Ondo State with regards to the various syncretism practices Yoruba Christian in Ikare Akoko are involved. The data collected indicates that the mean ratings of pastors for item 1 to 6 are 3.14, 3.25, 3.18, 3.22, 2.97 and 3.09 with corresponding standard deviation of 0.98, 0.87, 0.79, 0.11, 0.79 and 0.95. Also, the Church members mean rating for 1 to 6 shows 3.11, 3.27, 3.33, 2.92, 2.89 and 3.09 with corresponding standard of 0.81, 0.92, 0.83, 0.91, 0.12 and 0.99. Based on the condition of the study, the cut-off point of 2.50 both the Pastors and Church members rated items 1 to 6 as acceptable indicating that Yoruba Christian in Ikare Akoko are involved in the following syncretism practices; practice of secret cults/societies, belief in and practice of witchcraft, belief in black magic; charms and amulets, belief in ancestral/hero worship, belief in oracles/fortune telling; belief and participation in traditional festivals/rituals (*oro ile*).

Research Question Two: What are reasons for involving in the Aringinya festival in Ikare Akoko as a Christians?

Table two: Answer to Research Question two

Pastors Church Member

S/N	Reasons for participating in Aringinya festival Christian in Ikare-Akoko	SA	A	D	SD	X	SD	SA	A	D	SD	X	SD
7	Protection	72	6	0	0	3.11	0.93	348	129	84	38	3.18	0.97
8	Child bearing	48	24	0	0	2.91	0.82	388	189	58	11		
9	Riches and wealth	52	12	1	1	0.90	0.77	328	207	38	9	3.20	0.99
10	Power/influence	44	15	4	2	3.03	0.91	308	213	60	19	3.11	0.91
11	Culture tier	28	24	0	1	2.95	0.86	368	207	38	19	3.11	0.91
12	Great harvest.	64	12	0	0	3.10	0.92	148	219	38	7	3.01	0.95
13	Poverty	68	3	2	2	3.06	0.91	472	159	32	5	3.09	0.92
14	Materialism	56	3	2	1	3.01	0.85	136	192	40	4	2.99	0.89

Composite Mean 3.56

Source: Fieldwork 2022

The Table two above is to find out reasons why Yoruba Christians in Akoko are involving in the Aringinya festival in Ikare Akoko. The result collected from item seven (7) to twelve (14) had the following scores on part of the pastors; 3.11, 2.91, 2.89, 3.03, 2.95, 3.10, 3.06 and 3.01 with corresponding standard deviation of 0.93, 0.82, 0.77, 0.91, 0.86, 0.92, 0.91 and 0.85. The result indicates that the respondents all agreed that protection, child bearing, riches and wealth, power and influence, cultural tied, great harvest, poverty and materialism are the reasons why many Yoruba Christians in Ikare Akoko are participating in the ritual Aringinya festival.

The Church members also agreed on the item seven (7) to twelve (14), had the mean rating scores of; 3.18, 3.07, 3.20, 3.11, 3.0, 3.13, 3.09 and 2.99 with the corresponding standard deviation of 0.97, 0.93, 0.99, 0.91, 0.95, 0.93, 0.92 and 0.89. This indicated that protection, child bearing, riches and wealth, power and influence, cultural tied and for great harvest are the reasons for why some Christian in Ikare Akoko are participating in the ritual Aringinya festival in Ikare Akoko. The composite mean of 3.56 indicates that both Pastors and Church members accepted that that protection, child bearing, riches and wealth, power and influence, cultural tied and for great harvest are the reasons for why some Christian in Ikare Akoko are participating in the ritual Aringinya festival in Ikare Akoko.

3.1 Findings

Based on the outcome of the data analysis, the following has been summarized as the major findings of the study.

1. The Yoruba Christian in Ikare Akoko are involved in the following syncretism practices such as practice of secret cults/societies, belief in and practice of witchcraft, belief in black magic; charms and amulets, belief in ancestral/hero worship, belief in oracles/fortune telling; belief and participation in traditional festivals/rituals (*oro ile*).
2. The reasons why majorities of Yoruba Christians in Ikare Akoko are participating in the annual ritual Aringinya festival include; protection, child bearing (lack of patience), riches and wealth, power and healing, cultural tied, great harvest, poverty and materialism.

3.3 Discussion of Findings

The general objective of this study was to investigate various causes of syncretism among Yoruba Christians of Ikare - Akoko in Ondo State with focus on Aringinya festival in Ikare Akoko in Ondo State. Findings from the study reveals that Yoruba Christian in Ikare Akoko are involved practice of secret cults/societies, belief in and practice of witchcraft, belief in black magic; charms and amulets, belief in ancestral/hero worship, belief in oracles/fortune telling; belief and participation in traditional festivals/rituals (*oro ile*). This result is in line with the discovered of Ola (2014); Idowu 16 and Jude 18) who concluded that Yoruba Christians in South west Nigeria are involved in syncretic activities such as witchcraft, secret cults/societies and oracles/fortune telling. (Akinola 18) submitted that people from south west Nigeria weather Christians or Muslim are also found involve in traditional festivals, black magic; charms and amulets and belief in ancestral/hero worship. (Mwiti, Nderitu, and Nderitu 15)

The result indicates that protection, child bearing (lack of patience), riches and wealth, power and healing, cultural tied, great harvest, poverty and materialism are the reasons why many Yoruba Christians in Ikare Akoko are participating in the ritual Aringinya festival in Ikare Akoko, Ondo State. This collaborates with the finding of (Ojo 8) that concluded that many Yoruba Christians are engaged in traditional festivals to goodness or idols because of children, power, healing, deliverance, fruitiness, poverty and lack of patience. (Ezenweke & Kanu, 12) listed Geographical, economic and linguistic

factors facilitate syncretism among Christians. For instance, cosmopolitan cities or business nerve centres could breed syncretism. A case in point is the city of Alexandria, which favours cultural contacts, language dissemination and the interchange of gods (Chidili, 14). (Ezenweke et al, 12) identified policy of religious tolerance. In this case, syncretism becomes an effort to plug all the gaps in a given religion (Chidili, 14). The innovations in Christianity is said not to provide for some of the functions the traditional values perform. When traditional beliefs and practices which are not compatible with the Christian belief are included in the Christian faith, the result is syncretism (Gehman, 12).

3.4 Conclusion and recommendations

Based on the major findings of the study, the study hereby concludes that;

1. Yoruba Christian in Ikare Akoko are engages in the following syncretism practices; secret cults/societies, belief in and practice of witchcraft, belief in black magic; charms and amulets, belief in ancestral/hero worship, belief in oracles/fortune telling; belief and participation in traditional festivals/rituals (*oro ile*).
2. Yoruba Christians in Ikare Akoko are participating in the annual ritual Aringinya festival because of the following reasons; protection, child bearing (lack of patience), riches and wealth, power and healing, cultural tied, great harvest, poverty and materialism.

From the findings of this study, the following recommendations are hereby made.

1. The curriculum of the various Christians theology institutions could be overhauled with a view to meeting the modern challenges of education that are more relevant to the society. The few among these graduates educating and teaching against these practices should not relent in their efforts to eradicate syncretism among Yoruba society.
2. Regional crusade and revival and awareness could be mounted everywhere in Yoruba land with a view to making the Yoruba Christians and their clientele realise the evil effects of syncretism. They could be made to realise that Christianity is a perfect religion and it gives solution to all the various problems that face human existence. They could also consult trained guidance counsellors who can give professional advice on their various problems. They may be made to realize that their appeasements to the devils in various forms are not Biblical. They give the devil the opportunity to assume a position of importance and authority over their lives.

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